

IMPACT DAMAGE RESISTANCE AND DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF FIBRE METAL LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Low velocity and high velocity impact tests were performed on monolithic aluminium alloys, fibre metal laminates and carbon/thermoplastic composites to compare their damage resistance. Fibre metal laminates with glass fibres (GLARE) have a high damage resistance compared with aluminium and the carbon composite. Fatigue and residual strength tests were carried out on impact damaged panels. GLARE has a larger damaged area than aluminium after ballistic impact, but its residual strength was approximately equal. The residual strength after low velocity impact on fibre metal laminates is higher than the blunt notch strength when no crack or only a part through crack (on the non-impacted side) is present. After impact, the fibre metal laminates retain their superior fatigue resistance compared with aluminium alloys.

Keywords: Fibre Metal Laminates, ARALL, GLARE, Impact, Damage Tolerance

1. INTRODUCTION

The family of highly fatigue resistant fibre metal laminates ARALL and GLARE were developed primarily at Delft University over the past decade (Ref.1 to 6). The laminates are built up from thin high-strength aluminium alloy sheets bonded with strong fibre/adhesive prepregs. The prepregs are aramid or glass fibres in an epoxy adhesive. The variant with aramid fibres is usually called ARALL. GLARE incorporates glass fibres.

Fibre metal laminates were developed for their high fatigue resistance. This is achieved by fibre bridging of fatigue cracks in this hybrid material. If a crack has initiated in the aluminium alloy layers, some limited delamination will occur at the interfaces between the epoxy and the fibres. That will accommodate stress redistribution from the metal to unbroken fibres in the wake of the crack. Crack bridging provided by the strong fibres restrains crack opening, and thus reduces the driving force for crack growth in the metal layers, as seen in Figure 1. Fibre metal laminates combine the formability and machinability of aluminium alloys with the good fatigue resistance and high specific strength of composite materials. Fibre metal laminates can be plastically stretched after curing. After curing, residual tensile stresses exist in the aluminium layers alongside compressive stresses in the prepreg layers "Poststretching" causes a reversal of the residual stress system to compression in the aluminium and tension in the prepreg. The compressive stresses in the aluminium make the fatigue properties of the poststretched material even better than of the as-cured material.

Figure 1. Crack bridging in Fibre metal laminates.

The following grades are defined:

grade	Al alloy	fibre	orientation	poststretch
GLARE 1	7475-T76	glass	unidirectional	0.5%
GLARE 2	2024-T3			no
GLARE 3	2024-T3		50/50 cross-ply	no
GLARE 4	2024-T3		67/33 cross-ply	no
ARALL 1	7075-T6	aramid	unidirectional	0.4%
ARALL 2	2024-T3			no
ARALL 3	7475-T76			0.4%

The laminates are available in various thicknesses: e.g., a 3/2 lay-up means a laminate with three aluminium layers and two intermediate prepreg layers. As the table above shows, unidirectional and 0/90 cross-ply fibre lay-ups are available. Thus, a wide range of tailorable properties is available to the aircraft designer. ARALL 3 material is currently in production and flight test on the C-17 aft cargo door.

The sources of damage that threaten an aircraft in service can be divided into three main categories: fatigue, environmental degradation (corrosion) and incidental (impact) damage. The fatigue resistance of fibre metal laminates is so high that in well-designed structures, cracks that initiate will not grow large enough to cause a reduction of the strength below ultimate load. Fibre metal laminates also have a high environmental stability (Ref.4). Extensive testing showed that the adhesion between the aluminium and prepreg layers is excellent, even in aggressive environments. No relaxation of the residual stresses was measured. Moisture pickup by the resin was orders of magnitude slower than with conventional fibre/epoxy composites, because of the shielding effect of the outer aluminium layers. Corrosion pits penetrate no deeper than the outer aluminium layer, because the prepreg acts as a barrier. This leaves impact loading as a possible threat for fibre metal laminate structures. In this paper two aspects of the impact behaviour are discussed: impact damage resistance, or the performance of the material during the impact event, and damage tolerance, the fatigue and residual strength behaviour after the impact occurs.

2. IMPACT DAMAGE RESISTANCE

Impact damage to fibre metal laminates has been characterized extensively (Ref.6). Results

are shown here for ARALL 2, GLARE 3, 2024-T3 bare aluminium and a quasi-isotropic carbon fibre/thermoplastic composite known for its high toughness (APC-2). Sample thicknesses were $t=1.4$ mm for Al 2024-T3 and the laminates, and $t=2.0$ mm for APC-2, chosen to give approximately equal areal densities (mass per unit area). Because 1/4 mm thick GLARE 3 (areal density of 3.41 kg/m²) is expected to replace a thicker aluminium design, Al 2024-T3 clad with a thickness of 1.6 mm (areal density= 4.45 kg/m²) was tested also. This represents the Airbus A340 fuselage material. The specimens had a clamped area of 100 mm square and were impacted in the centre by a 7.5 mm radius hemispherical steel impactor. Low-velocity tests (up to 10 m/s) were performed using an instrumented drop-tower arrangement; the impactor mass was 575 g. High velocity tests (up to 100 m/s) were carried out using an instrumented gas gun; in this case the projectile mass was 23.3 g.

Figure 2. Minimum cracking energy of the materials.

Figure 2 compares the minimum energies required to cause visible cracking. For an equal areal density, the minimum cracking energy of GLARE 3 is superior to Al 2024-T3 and APC-2 carbon/PEEK for static and dynamic loading. When GLARE 3 and the heavier baseline 2024-T3 ($t=1.6$ mm) are compared, one sees that GLARE has a higher first cracking energy at low and high velocity impact. The superior behaviour of GLARE is caused by the influence of the strain rate on the strength of the glass fibre (Ref.6). The minimum cracking energy of carbon/PEEK is poor compared with Al 2024-T3 and GLARE 3. The delaminated area in the GLARE 3 material is much smaller than in the thermoplastic composites. The superior behaviour of GLARE 3 is illustrated by Figure 3, which shows specimens impacted

at 100 J at a high velocity.

Figure 3. Damaged specimens (impact energy 100 J, high velocity).

The testing device shown in Figure 4 was used to study the behaviour of 1.4 mm thick GLARE 3 and 1.6 mm thick Al 2024-T3 clad under biaxial loading. This arrangement simulates small engine fragments hitting a pressurized aircraft fuselage. A steel projectile simulating such a fragment (Figure 4) with a diameter of 20 mm and a mass of 54 g was shot with a velocity of 400 m/s through the centre of the specimen. The width of the specimen at the load introduction was 160 mm; the loaded specimens were biaxially loaded with a load of 35 kN. This results in a biaxial stress field of 137 MPa for 2024-T3 and 156 MPa for GLARE 3. The homogeneity and the intensity of the stress field was checked with strain gage measurements. One unloaded Al 2024-T3, two unloaded GLARE 3, two biaxially loaded 2024-T3 and three biaxially loaded GLARE 3 specimens were tested. After the ballistic tests, specimens were cut into 160 mm wide rectangles and pulled to failure under static loading.

Figure 4. Testing device for biaxial loading and fragment simulating projectile.

Figure 5 shows that considerable damage is created at the back (projectile exit) side of the GLARE specimens. The fragment peels off the thin aluminium layer at the back side of the laminate. The biaxial loading had no effect on the size of the observed damage. Although the damage size in GLARE is greater than in 2024-T3, the residual load carrying capability of

both materials is similar, as is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Damage in Al 2024-T3 and GLARE 3 after ballistic impact (back side, biaxial loading 35 kN).

Figure 6. Failure load at residual strength test after ballistic impact.

3. DAMAGE TOLERANCE

Fatigue and residual strength tests were carried out on standard 3/2 lay-ups of cross-ply GLARE and unidirectional ARALL with damage typically encountered in service. Test specimens were 300 mm long and 160 mm wide, and were subjected to low-velocity impact with the same set-up described in the previous section. Impact energies ranged up to 13 J for ARALL 3 ($t = 1.33 \text{ mm}$) and 44 J for GLARE 3 ($t = 1.40 \text{ mm}$), which produced a scope of damage from dents with no cracking to perforation. The specimens were subjected to constant amplitude fatigue at stress amplitudes and cycles considered typical for potential fuselage

applications before residual strength testing.

Figure 7. Residual strength of ARALL 3 after impact and fatigue.

After impact, a residual stress system is present in the dent. Tensile stresses exist at the centre of the impacted (concave) side while compression occurs on the convex side due to spring back. When the impacted specimen with the dent is subjected to overall tension - as in the present fatigue tests - a complex combination of bending and extension occurs in the dent. This allows the convex surface - the non impacted side, usually inside the structure - to remain in compression up to very high gross stress levels. Tensile strains occur in the heavily deformed region at the edge of the dent on the impacted side. These tensile strains are caused by a stress concentration due to the lower effective stiffness of the dent, and can have a magnitude of 1.5 to 2 times the nominal strains outside the dent (Ref.6).

ARALL 3 specimens were impacted, then subjected to 20,000 cycles at 5-105 MPa before residual strength testing. Cracks due to impact in ARALL 3 occurred perpendicular to the fibre direction. The perforating impact at 13 J resulted in a Y-shaped branched crack. In no case did the cracks caused by impact grow during fatigue cycling. The gross residual strength after impact is shown in Figure 7. The results show that while ARALL is sensitive to impact damage, perforation (through cracking) occurs before the blunt notch strength is compromised.

GLARE 3 specimens were impacted and subjected to constant amplitude fatigue loading at 6-120 MPa before residual strength testing at 270,000 cycles. In contrast with ARALL 3, cracks in GLARE 3 due to impact always occurred parallel to the metal rolling (L) direction. In the specimens loaded in the L direction, crack growth during fatigue cycling occurred only on the front (impacted) side of the 38 and 44 J samples, after 160,000 and 90,000 cycles, respectively. Cracks initiated and grew slowly not from the centre, but from the heavily plastically deformed radius of the dents. These cracks were confined to only the surface layer. Of the specimens loaded in LT direction, only the 37 J specimen showed any fatigue crack growth, which again was confined to the front metal layer.

Figure 8. Fatigue behaviour of Al 2024-T3 and GLARE 3 after perforating impacts.

Figure 9. Residual strength of GLARE 3 after impact and fatigue.

None of the GLARE 3 specimens with penetrating impact failed in 270,000 cycles. A comparison of GLARE and 2024-T3 for penetrating impacts in the range from 37 to 46 J is shown in Figure 8. The GLARE specimens exhibited slow crack growth in one surface layer. The damage in 2024-T3 did not grow until 180,000 cycles, but then grew very rapidly to failure in a few thousand additional cycles. The GLARE 3 specimens were pulled statically to failure after 270,000 cycles; Figure 9 shows the residual strength.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Fibre metal laminates with glass fibres (GLARE) show a superior resistance to low and high velocity impact damage (expressed in the minimum cracking energy) compared with Al 2024-T3 and carbon/thermoplastic composites. The damage size of GLARE after impact is significantly smaller than of quasi-isotropic carbon/PEEK with equal areal density.
2. GLARE shows significantly more damage after ballistic impact by projectiles simulating engine fragments, but this damage is primarily present in the outer aluminium layer on the exit side. The residual load-carrying capability of GLARE is in this case equal to monolithic aluminium 2024-T3 of 30% higher areal density.
3. The post-impact residual strength of fibre metal laminates is higher than the blunt notch strength while no through-crack is present.
4. Crack growth occurs at high stress levels in ARALL (fibre metal laminate with aramid fibre) and GLARE, but is confined to the aluminium layer at the impacted side (outside the structure).

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